

BACKGROUND AND RATIONALE FOR STUDYING PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS IN POLITICAL DISCOURSE

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Phraseological units play a crucial role in political discourse, shaping the language used by politicians to convey their messages and influence public opinion. These linguistic constructs, which include idioms, collocations, proverbs, and other fixed expressions, carry a significant weight in political communication due to their cultural resonance, rhetorical impact, and persuasive power. Understanding the semantic properties of phraseological units within a lexical semantic framework is of great importance for several reasons.

Effective Communication: Phraseological units in political discourse serve as powerful tools for effective communication. Politicians often employ these expressions to encapsulate complex ideas, convey emotions, and simplify complex policy issues for the general public. By using familiar and resonant phrases, politicians can establish connections with their audience, enhance their persuasive abilities, and effectively communicate their key messages.

Persuasive Techniques: Phraseological units are instrumental in political persuasion. Politicians strategically employ well-known idiomatic expressions and collocations to evoke emotional responses, create memorable slogans, and shape public perception. By utilizing these linguistic devices, politicians can tap into shared cultural and social values, reinforcing their political agenda and ideologies.

Studying and developing phraseological units in linguistics has been a subject of interest for many researchers throughout history. Here are some notable scientists, periods, and works related to this field:

1. Wolfgang Mieder: A prominent phraseologist known for his extensive research on proverbs and idioms. His work includes numerous publications on the origins, meanings, and cultural significance of phraseological units.
2. Charles Fillmore: A linguist who contributed to the development of Frame Semantics, a theory that explores the semantic structure of linguistic expressions, including phraseological units.

3. Anatoly Liberman: Renowned for his scholarship on etymology, folklore, and phraseology. Liberman's works delve into the historical development and evolution of phraseological units, particularly in the context of the English language.

4. The Prague School: A group of linguists from Prague who made significant contributions to the study of phraseology, particularly through their focus on collocations and word combinations in language.

5. Corpus Linguistics: The emergence of corpus linguistics as a methodology for studying language has greatly impacted the analysis of phraseological units. Researchers utilize large corpora of authentic language data to investigate the usage patterns and distribution of phraseological units in different contexts.

6. Computational Linguistics: With advancements in natural language processing and machine learning, computational linguistics plays a crucial role in the analysis and extraction of phraseological units from textual data.

7. Lexicography: Lexicographers have compiled dictionaries and databases specifically dedicated to phraseological units, providing comprehensive resources for researchers and language learners alike.

These scientists, periods, and works have collectively contributed to the understanding and development of phraseological units in linguistics, shedding light on their structure, semantics, and usage in language.

Wolfgang Mieder's work on proverbs and idioms encompasses a wide range of topics within the field of phraseology. Here are some key aspects of his research:

1. Origins and Evolution: Mieder has delved into the origins and historical evolution of proverbs and idioms, tracing their roots in oral tradition and folklore across different cultures and languages. His research often involves exploring the migration and adaptation of proverbs and idioms through time and space.

Meanings and Interpretations: One of Mieder's primary interests is in uncovering the meanings and interpretations of proverbs and idioms within their cultural and linguistic contexts. He examines how these phraseological units convey wisdom, values, and social norms, and how their meanings may vary across different communities and generations.

Cultural Significance: Mieder's work highlights the cultural significance of proverbs and idioms as repositories of shared knowledge and collective wisdom within societies. He explores how proverbs and idioms reflect cultural attitudes,

beliefs, and worldviews, and how they are used to express complex ideas and emotions in succinct and memorable ways.

Comparative Studies: Mieder engages in comparative studies of proverbs and idioms from diverse linguistic and cultural backgrounds, drawing parallels and contrasts between different traditions and systems of expression. His research sheds light on the universal themes and motifs found in proverbial wisdom across human societies.

Applications: Mieder's research on proverbs and idioms has practical applications in fields such as education, literature, language teaching, and cross-cultural communication. He explores how proverbs and idioms can be used as teaching tools, literary devices, and cultural markers in various contexts.

Publications: Mieder has authored and edited numerous publications on proverbs and idioms, including books, articles, and reference works. His writings are characterized by meticulous scholarship, interdisciplinary approach, and engaging style, making them valuable resources for scholars, students, and enthusiasts of phraseology.

Overall, Wolfgang Mieder's work on proverbs and idioms has made significant contributions to the field of phraseology, enriching our understanding of these linguistic phenomena and their role in human communication and culture.

2. Charles Fillmore's contributions to the study of phraseological units primarily stem from his development of Frame Semantics, a linguistic theory that investigates the semantic structure of linguistic expressions, including phrases and idiomatic constructions. While Fillmore's work is more broadly focused on semantics, his theory has implications for understanding the meaning and usage of phraseological units. Here's more information about Fillmore's work and its relevance to phraseology:

1. **Frame Semantics:** Fillmore introduced Frame Semantics in the late 1970s as an alternative to traditional lexical semantics, which focuses primarily on the meanings of individual words. According to Frame Semantics, words and phrases derive their meaning from the cognitive "frames" or conceptual structures in which they are used. These frames represent typical situations, events, or scenarios and provide a context for interpreting linguistic expressions, including phraseological units.

Conceptual Structures: In Frame Semantics, Fillmore proposed that language users possess mental representations of conceptual structures called "frames," which organize knowledge about specific domains of experience. These frames consist of slots, or elements, representing various components of a conceptual

category, and fillers, which are the specific entities or attributes associated with each slot.

FrameNet: Fillmore and his colleagues developed FrameNet, a computational resource that catalogs lexical units (including phraseological units) in terms of the frames they evoke and the semantic roles they play within those frames. FrameNet provides a systematic framework for analyzing the meaning and usage of linguistic expressions across different contexts and domains.

Application to Phraseology: While Fillmore's primary focus was on semantics, his theory of Frame Semantics has implications for understanding the meaning and structure of phraseological units. Phraseological units often evoke specific frames or conceptual domains, and their interpretation depends on the context in which they are used. Frame Semantics provides a theoretical framework for analyzing how phraseological units derive their meaning from underlying conceptual structures.

Influence on Linguistics: Fillmore's work on Frame Semantics has had a profound impact on various subfields of linguistics, including computational linguistics, cognitive linguistics, and construction grammar. His ideas have influenced research on language processing, language acquisition, and cross-linguistic typology, contributing to a deeper understanding of how language is structured and understood by speakers.

In summary, while Charles Fillmore's work is not exclusively focused on phraseological units, his theory of Frame Semantics provides valuable insights into the semantic structure of linguistic expressions, including phrases and idiomatic constructions, and has implications for the study of phraseology.

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